

Paper ID #

On Intelligent Driver Monitoring based on smart-devices

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Abstract

Autonomous driving is undoubtedly the future of the automotive industry. However, the complete migration to those technologies is not a short-term goal and it will not happen simultaneously throughout the world. Thus, existing technologies such the Driver State Monitoring systems are still relevant and could potentially foresee and prevent the occurrence of accidents. To this end, in this paper we present IRIS, a Driver State Monitoring Android application, which aims at providing a real-time monitoring and assessment of the drowsiness and inattention level of a driver. IRIS is based on an on-device machine learning analysis of incoming frames from the front camera of a smartphone and is able to notify the driver through a set of alerts about his/her status. A set of on-road experiments was conducted to validate the feasibility of the solution.

Keywords: Android Driver State Monitoring system, driver behaviour

Introduction

It is an undeniable truth that vehicle automation is the headliner of today's automotive sector and that all companies, from the biggest to the smallest, aim at designing and presenting a highly autonomous vehicle within the next years. However, the shift from manual and semi-autonomous vehicles to fully autonomous technologies still requires time and research and is not foreseen in the near future. Hence, as long as the interaction among the driver and the vehicle is still active, meaning that the driving activity can be performed by either of them, existing technologies such as the Driver State Monitoring systems (DSM) could offer an extra level of security by providing meaningful insights on the mental and physical state of the driver and his ability to perform the related tasks.

A DSM system is usually exploited within a vehicle in order to estimate the general state of the driver either in terms of fatigue or in terms of his/her distraction level. Considering the statistics emerging from several studies, such the one from Canada [1] which reports that 20% of fatalities during a collision involve fatigue, or the one from Pakistan [2] which relates 34% of road accidents to fatigue or the survey from US [3] which reports that around 20% of car accidents are closely connected to drowsiness of the driver, it is becoming evident that monitoring the state of the driver is of crucial importance and can potentially prevent accidents on the road.

To this end, many multinational automotive companies and third-party companies have invested resources in order to design and implement their own DSM systems. Back in 2008, Toyota installed Crown, their first fatigue detection system responsible for monitoring the eyelid activity, while recently they deployed the Toyota Safety Sense P [4] which includes features such as lane and pedestrian

detection. In 2016 Nissan implemented Nissan Maxima [5] which monitors the steering patterns of the driver while in 2017 Volkswagen presented Rest Assist [6] which evaluates the steering wheel movements, the use of the pedals and the interaction with the road lanes. Last but not least in 2019, Volvo also announced their intention of developing a camera-based build-in system to detect drunk and drowsy drivers [7]. With respect to the third-party companies two of the newest attempts on DSM systems are the MR688 by Care Driver's [8] which based on camera footage tracks the pupil of the driver and his/her head movements, and the OpGuard designed by GuardVant [9] which by analysing video frames from an installed camera is able to monitor the eyelid closure, the head pose and if the driver is distracted by a phone.

Although the driver's state monitoring and assessment has gained a lot of attention the past few years amongst the research community and the automotive industry, there is still not such framework or regulation that will define a universally accepted condition of what is considered a safe driver state. In general, the notion of the driver's state can be seen as a set of conditions that affect the driver in a particular instance of the driving session. The most exploited variables for the assessment of the distraction and/or the drowsiness of the driver include the monitoring of the driver's head movements and the tracking of the eyes [10-13].

With the latest technological advances and with the sensors becoming less intrusive and noticeable, researchers are trying to enhance the development of the DSM systems by considering also biometric measurements such as the Heart Rate (HR) or the Heart Rate Variability (HRV). Several studies suggest that both of the aforementioned metrics could be good indicators for the vigilance state [14] – [16] and have tried to investigate the relation among driver's fatigue and those parameters [17] – [19].

With respect to the significant contributions made by the aforementioned studies, it has been clearly spotted that their main disadvantage is not on the designing of highly accurate individual DSM techniques, but the absence of an integrated system that will combine all the aforementioned goodies in a single mobile framework. It was also spotted in most cases, that there is a significant but neglected need of introducing and leveraging additional auxiliary equipment on-board, such as cameras, sensors and particular tailored hardware for the collection, analysis and assessment of the state of the driver.

Considering and trying to cope with those deficiencies, we present in this paper IRIS, a DSM Android Application, which aims at providing a real-time monitoring and assessment of the drowsiness and inattention level of a driver. IRIS is a standalone Android application which utilizes the front camera of a smartphone in order to monitor the driver throughout the whole driving session and exploits on-device machine learning algorithms to estimate his/her fatigue and distraction level. For the estimation, IRIS focuses on both physical and biological signs. Physical signs include the eye closure and by extension the percent of time the eyes are closed (PERCLOS), the yawning frequency and the head pose. Regarding the biological signs, IRIS considers the HR of the driver which is retrieved in real-time from a wearable device. If the results of the estimations indicate that the driver is either distracted or tired, the IRIS application throws the appropriate alerts both in the form of sound alerts and in the form of prompt messages on the smartphone. The analysis is conducted in a per frame basis and the obtained results from the algorithms are also saved in a JSON file in order to be available for further analysis

after the driving session is concluded. Extensive data collection within Catalink premises and thorough experiments have been conducted on the road in order to validate the feasibility of the proposed solution. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Firstly, we discuss in detail the IRIS application and the followed methodology. Afterwards, we refer to the conducted experiments and the obtained results and finally we conclude the paper.

IRIS Android Application

It is a fact that the big automotive industries are trying to introduce new safety and security systems in their new generation cars, with a big number of sensors and actuators which will be responsible for monitoring the driver, the vehicle, their interaction and the overall environment inside and outside of the car. However, the number of people who are not able to have access to this technology is not negligible and therefore solutions that can provide the same safety measurements should also be available via other means.

In this direction and considering that the most available and most exploitable object nowadays is undoubtedly the smartphones, we have designed and implemented IRIS, which is a DSM Android application that provides a real-time monitoring and assessment of the drowsiness and distraction level of the driver without the need of introducing several external obtrusive devices such as cameras, sensors etc. The estimations are conducted utilizing Google's ML Kit¹, a standalone library which offers the possibility of on-device machine learning processing. More specifically, ML Kit provides the means of integrating machine learning capabilities into an application, through the exposure of the so-called vision APIs. Those APIs refer to both video and image analysis and can be exploited in a great deal of use cases such as face detection, barcode scanning, pose detection, text recognition etc. Within the IRIS application ML KIT was utilized to achieve a fast, efficient and real-time face recognition and facial landmarks extraction.

Monitoring and assessment of the physical signs

The physical signs that IRIS considers are the eye closure and the yawning frequency for estimating the drowsiness and the head pose of the driver for estimating the distraction level. The application utilizes the front camera of the smartphone and thus the only prerequisite is to place the device in front of the driver in a place where the face is clearly visible and within the camera frame. The user interface of the application alongside with the on-board set-up of the device are shown in Figure 1.

Once the driver initiates the session, the front camera of the smartphone is engaged and a sequence of steps is taking place. First, the detection algorithm returns as a result the detection and the localization of the face within the frame and the extraction of the facial landmarks alongside with their coordinates. As facial landmarks we consider points of interest within a face such as the eyes (right and left), cheeks, nose, lips and eyebrows. Figure 2 depicts the localization of the aforementioned points in a frame taken by IRIS application both in conditions with and without sufficient light.

¹ <https://developers.google.com/ml-kit/>

Figure 1 – User Interface of IRIS application (a)-(b) and set up on driver’s car (c).

As a second step, the retrieved landmarks and their coordinates are utilized in order to determine i) if the driver has his/her eyes closed (either one of them or both of them), ii) if the driver is yawning and iii) if the driver is looking left or right with respect to the camera. More specifically, the main functionalities of the IRIS application are the following:

1. **Eye closure and PERCLOS:** the application is able to locate and track the eyes of the driver by taking advantage of included functionalities of the ML Kit library. More specifically ML Kit’s face detector provides the possibility of having the eyes closed. If this possibility surpasses the defined threshold for a number of consecutive frames, then a sound alert is raised in order to awake the driver.
2. **Yawning detection:** the application is able to define if a driver is yawning by making use of the MAR (Mouth Aspect Ration) algorithm. More specifically, the ML Kit face detection results into a set of 38 points for the mouth as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2– ML Kit face detection (mouth points)

From those points we utilized points 3 ,4 and 5 both from the bottom and the upper lip alongside with points 0 and 10 which are the edges of the mouth. Having the coordinates of those points we calculated the MAR using the following equation:

$$MAR = \frac{||UL_3 - DL_5|| + ||UL_4 - DL_4|| + ||UL_5 - DL_3||}{2||EDG_0 - EDG_{10}||}$$

Where UL_x , DL_x and EDG_x refer respectively to the x_{th} point of the Upper Lip, Down Lip and the Edge of the mouth. If for a number of frames within a specified timeframe the driver is yawning, then the application throws a prompt message suggesting a break.

3. **Head pose:** the application is able to determine if the face orientation of the driver by utilizing information extracted from the ML Kit library regarding the angle of the face with respect to the camera. If the calculations show that the driver is looking right or left for a number of consecutive frames, indicating that his/her attention is not on the road, the application throws a prompt alert to notify the driver that he/she may be distracted.

It is worth mentioning that the driver has the ability to switch off the preview of the camera, so as not to feel being monitored and/or distracted and perform the driving activities in a normal way. At this case, the screen will show a simple animation and the analysis will happen in the background. Last but not least, the application does not store, share, or send outside the device the captured video frames, safeguarding thus the privacy of the driver. IRIS is conducting an on-device analysis and the frames are discarded after the above estimations have been conducted.

Monitoring and assessment of the biological signs

The combination of the above features with biological signs could result in a more robust and holistic approach on estimating the state of the driver and capturing on time early signs of fatigue. Biological signs may include heart, brain and skin based signals and the noticeable changes of those has proven to be an accurate method to detect fatigue [20]. In order not to disrupt the driver with several intrusive sensors, for the implementation of IRIS DSM solution we utilized another widely accepted device, the smartwatches. In particular, alongside with the IRIS application we have also developed a companion watch application which can be installed in smartwatches running the Wear OS². The watch application is responsible for monitoring continuously the heart rate of the driver and transmit the measurements to the handheld application. The heart rate value is also visible on a small box in the preview of the camera of the handheld application as it is depicted in the following Figures. The communication among the two applications is bilateral, meaning that they can both receive and send messages to each other. Consequently, if the HR of the driver reaches a low value which may indicate that he/she is feeling sleepy and may lose control a sound notification will appear on the smartphone and at the same time the driver will feel a vibration on his/her wrist from the watch. The same communication occurs when IRIS

² <https://wearos.google.com/>

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detects that the driver has his/her eyes closed. A sound alarm is fired on the handheld application and a vibration on the watch.

Validation

The validation of the proposed solution was conducted through a set of on-road experiments. The requirement for those experiments was the existence of a smartphone powered by Android with the minimum Android version being the 8.0 (Oreo) and the existence of a smartwatch powered by Wear OS. Both applications were installed on the devices and the scenarios that the users were asked to experiment with are the following: i) keep their eyes closed for a few seconds, ii) yawn several times for a few minutes and iii) look right or left for a few seconds. With respect to the HR monitoring evaluation and considering that lowering the HR on demand is a very difficult task, we kept the thresholds rather high (around 65bpm) in order to be able to check the flawless communication among the handheld and the watch application. Furthermore, a driving session was also carried out during night in order to test the application under the absence of sufficient light. Figure 3 depicts several screenshots obtained during the session, where IRIS estimated high levels of drowsiness and distraction and presented the necessary messages.

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Figure 3: (a) Sound Alarm when user keeps his/her eyes closed for a number of consecutive frames; (b) Prompt message when the user is yawning many times within a specified timeframe; (c) Prompt message when the user looks right or left for a number of consecutive frames; (d) Validation test on different device

and person; (e) Yawning alarm on different device and person; (f) An animation is depicted if the user chooses not to see the footage from the front camera; (g) Localization of the landmarks in low light conditions; (h) Prompt message when the user looks right or left for a number of consecutive frames in low light conditions; (i) Companion watch application;

The results and the feedback that we obtained from the conducted experiments indicate that IRIS is able to immediately respond to the events of interest by firing the sound alarms and/or prompting the necessary messages. False positives were presented during the yawn detection, fact that indicates that a fine-tuning of the MAR algorithm could be considered, perhaps by including more points of the mouth. Moreover, we observed during the night experiments that with a complete absence of light the application fails to detect the face of the driver. Although, when there are lights on the road IRIS is able to conduct the analysis.

Conclusion

This paper presents IRIS, a DSM system which consists of a handheld Android application and a companion watch application. The first utilizes the front camera of the smartphone in order to provide a continuous evaluation of the state of the driver through the monitoring of the eye closure, the yawning activity and the head pose, whilst the later is responsible for retrieving and reporting to the handheld application the heart rate of the driver. Both of the applications are able to fire alarms and/or display messages when necessary to awake the driver. As future work we plan to develop, train and integrate our own models for drowsiness and distraction detection. By this way we will be able to parametrize and fine tune the models based on the needs of the application and achieve better results. Additionally, we plan to exploit the Heart Rate Variability measurements, instead of raw HR measurements, in order to enhance the ability of our drowsiness detection model. Our aim is to make a model which is able to capture the inter-driver variabilities and thus score higher accuracy rates. Finally, an extended testbed will be set up, where a number of different users will test on the road the application under different circumstances in order to validate its efficiency and its accuracy.

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